

Relation Study of Chemerin Protein Effects at the Obesity Status

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Suggested Citation

Khalaf, M.S. (2024). Relation Study of Chemerin Protein Effects at the Obesity Status. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 462-465.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).40](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).40)

Abstract:

Obesity is a metabolic disorder characterized by increased body mass in humans and is accompanied by multiple health complications and many disorders, and is classified based on the body mass index. Chemerin is a protein encoded by white fat cells and plays an important role in metabolism in obese people. The current study showed that chemerin increases with increasing body mass and due to its important functions, it can be used as a regulatory factor for metabolism in obese people.

Keywords: Obesity, Body mass index, chemerin, adipose cells.

Introduction

Obesity

Obesity can be defined as a disorder caused by the accumulation of excess fats in the body tissues, which in turn leads to an increase in body weight. The danger of this disorder is considered silent because the symptoms and signs of the appearance of complications of the disorder are delayed in appearing (Piché, Tchernof, & Després, 2020). Obesity is assessed in the body using the body mass index (BMI) method, where the body weight (measured in units of Kg) is divided by the square of the body height (measured in units of m²). An increase in BMI leads to major health complications and complex diseases, such as IR disorder, which in turn leads to type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, joint diseases such as osteoarthritis and other disorders. The value of BMI is classified according to the World Health Organization (WHO) into (Afzal, et al., 2021):

- Normal (when BMI < 25.0 kg/m²)

- Overweight (when BMI 25.0 - 29.9 kg/m²)
- Obese (when BMI ≥ 30.0 kg/m²)

The Obesity is also sub-classified into:

- Class I (when BMI 30.0 -34.9 kg/m²)
- Class II (when BMI 35.0 -39.9 kg/m²)
- Class III (BMI ≥ 40.0 kg/m²)

The main cause of obesity disorder is the energy imbalance between energy consumption and energy intake. The presence of unconsumed calories leads to their transformation into fat accumulated in the visceral tissues of the body (Omer, 2020). However, there are other causes that lead to the creation of this imbalance, which are:

Food Intake and Energy Balance

The causes of obesity are many and varied but the most important is the imbalance between calories expenditure and gained. This means that there are quantities of calories accumulated in the body due to a rich calories diet, especially in

recent years, society has witnessed the spread of eating meals rich in calories. This has been proven by many studies conducted on Iraqi society and other societies, as it has been proven that an increase in meals rich in calories leads to an increase in body weight and on a continuous basis in society (Hall, et al., 2022).

Family History

Having a family history of obesity is activated by the presence of obesity factors such as unhealthy diet, lack of exercise, etc. This means that if one of the parents is obese, it leads to a high percentage of children becoming obese in the future (Beltrán-Carrillo, et al., 2022).

Microenvironment and Gut Microbiome

Many studies have shown that there is a gastric bacterial environment that helps in weight gain and causes obesity. These infectious conditions make people more susceptible to obesity and also more susceptible to other diseases, as such conditions are often hereditary (Geng, et al., 2022).

Epigenetic Modification

The genome plays an important role in causing obesity, as there is a single genome that is a major cause of weight gain and obesity. However, in recent studies, the idea of lifestyle has overcome the idea of genetic causation of obesity (Littleton, Berkowitz, & Grant, 2020).

Obesity disorder is currently considered one of the most widespread disorders in the world, which causes an unhealthy life and, due to its complications, may cause death for the affected person.

Chemerin

Chemerin is known as a member of the adipokine family, and is called in some sources tazarotene-induced gene 2 protein (TIG2), chemerin is encoded by the RARRES2 gene. Chemerin is chemically classified as an inactive protein, as it is converted to the active form by cleavage of the C-terminal by special proteins called serine proteases (which are of two types: procoagulant and inflammatory), see figure 1.

Figure 1. Chemerin Structure

The molecular weight of chemerin is about 14 kD in its inactive state. Chemerin acts as a ligand for G protein-coupled receptors to stimulate

macrophages to migrate to sites of inflammation by activating chemotaxis (Zhao, Leung, & Morser, 2022). On the other hand, it is believed

that chemerin acts as a receptor on the surfaces of cells for retinoids. The chemerin compound is produced mainly by white adipose tissue in the liver and lung, and because it act to regulate glucose uptake and adipose cell differentiation, it is classified as one of the members of the adipokines (Pluta, et al., 2020).

Experiments conducted first on mice showed that the level of chemerin begins to rise in adipose cells after differentiation, but before that, the level of chemerin cannot be detected (Yu, et al., 2022). In other experiments, it was

discovered that chemerin suppression causes a decrease in the level of glucose transporters called (GLUT4) as well as adiponectin and leptin, which in turn shows the effective role of chemerin in sugar and fat metabolism for mature adipose cells. On the other hand, other studies were conducted that showed that chemerin contributes to cellular fat metabolism by mediating phosphorylation processes, as it excites Mitogen-activated protein kinase 1 (MAPK 1), which participates in fat breakdown (Su, et al., 2021), see figure 2.

Figure 2. Chemerin Functions

Chemerin plays an important role in causing obesity due to its effective function in chronic inflammation processes and phagocytic cells, as it is secreted from white adipose tissue and not brown adipose tissue. This has been proven through experiments, where it was found that chemerin levels increase with increasing body mass, diabetes and insulin resistance, as it was noted that these individuals have high triglyceride levels and also suffer from high blood pressure. On the other hand, there are experiments that prove that chemerin levels play

a role in regulating sugar levels in people who are overweight, which means that chemerin could be a therapeutic target in the future for type 2 diabetes (Acharyya, Dutta, & Sengupta, 2023).

Conclusions

The present study summarizes the importance of the role of chemerin in human obesity disorder, as the present study presented the role of chemerin in inflammatory processes as well as phagocytic processes, and also showed that chemerin increases with the increase in body

mass, and therefore it can be used as a therapeutic agent because it increases in obese people and works to regulate fat and sugar metabolism

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our gratitude to every one for their help to complete this article.

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